

Orbital Dynamic Simulation and Passive Attitude Control of CubeSats

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Abstract—This work reports the study of an orbital simulation used to analyze passive attitude control systems of CubeSats. Such control system aims to guide the satellite's body without any electrical energy consumption. The simulation is a complete orbital study that considers several factors, such as: i) the rotation of the planet; ii) the body's attitude; iii) the geomagnetic field, etc. The satellite's attitude is influenced by some physical phenomena, such as the interaction between the magnetic elements within the satellite's body and the magnetic field of the Earth, the gravity gradient, among others. The operating principle of this control system is based on the alignment of the magnetic field of the magnets embedded in the CubeSat's body with the local geomagnetic field, so that the nanosatellite follows the lines of the Earth's magnetic field at any given point. Hysteresis rods composed of a high permeability material are also used, to dissipate the energy of the system during the process of attitude correction. An 1U (10cm edge cube) CubeSat is used to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method. The complete translational and rotational movement is simulated for low Earth orbits with altitudes of 300 km and 600 km. Different conditions of orbital inclination and eccentricity were also experimented. As it is demonstrated by the results, the proposed method can provide the time evolution of the CubeSat variables along the orbital flight. Such feature is not only useful to simulate the satellite at the given conditions, as it enables improvements at the attitude control system, by using other pointing strategies.

Index Terms—ADCS, Orbital Simulation, Passive Magnetic Attitude Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The nanosatellites industry has been conquering a large market in recent years, as it is also an exceptional tool for learning and studying. The CubeSat is an example of a nanosatellite which size is standardized by 10 cm edge cubes. These satellites are composed of several subsystems with different functions, one of which is the Attitude Control and Determination Subsystems (ADCS). This subsystem is of great importance for the satellite, being critical for other subsystems, such as telemetry and communication, thermal control, among others [1]. The ADCS is responsible for stabilizing the nanosatellite and pointing it to desired directions during the mission, despite external disturbances.

Control systems for CubeSats are divided into active and passive. Active systems maintain the satellite's attitude by measuring its orientation on the three axes and making corrections based on these measurements. This strategy is especially important when a fine level of positioning is demanded, although resulting in a heavier, more complex and a more expensive CubeSat. Some control strategies involve magnetorquers and/or reaction wheels [2], drag maneuvering

[3], electric propulsion [4], among others. Passive systems, on the other hand, maintain a raw orientation without spending energy [5]. Although the positioning precision is not the main feature of passive systems, such kind of CubeSats is yet present in important scientific application, as in space-weather research [6]. The focus of this work is on a specific passive control system called Passive Magnetic Control System (PMACS).

The control system aims to control the orientation of the satellite in relation to a reference. The working principle of the PMACS is the alignment of the magnetic field produced by the magnets fixed on the CubeSat's body with the local geomagnetic field, so that the orientation of the satellite varies according to the geomagnetic field along the orbit. Furthermore, hysteresis rods are used to dissipate rotational energy during the attitude correction process [7]. In order to know the efficiency of the proposed control system, it is necessary to develop a simulation of the trajectory that the satellite will make around the Earth. This trajectory is an orbital study that considers the interaction between the magnetic elements present in the CubeSat's body and the Earth's magnetic field, together with other torques, such as the gravity gradient and aerodynamic torque [8].

Some other papers analyzed the CubeSat's flight simulation but did not consider some conditions discussed in this paper. For instance, a passive magnetic controller is studied in [9], however only circular orbits are discussed. In addition, the gravity-gradient and the aerodynamic disturbances were neglected. A CubeSat in an 800km polar circular orbit is considered in [10], but the aerodynamic disturbance is rarely important at this altitude. A more complete study was presented in [7], where aerodynamic appendages are developed as an attitude control strategy. However, the authors only considered circular orbits too. Many other studies developed active control methodologies, but the environmental conditions were not the main concern, e.g. [2-4].

The objective of this work is to study the passive magnetic attitude control system through a complete orbital simulation. The most important environmental disturbances are described and modelled. The simulation considers any orbital shape, by an unconstrained adjustment of the inclination and the eccentricity. In what refers to the aerodynamic influence on the CubeSat body, we also present a simplified way to model the phenomenon. Furthermore, some aspects on the passive magnetic orientation of the CubeSat are reinforced and highlighted.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

From the equation of the rigid body dynamics, it is possible to present the rotation of a rigid body using the Euler equation [8].

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It is important to note that the vectors are written in the reference system that coincides with the axes of inertia of the satellite's body. Thus, the equation (1) is as follows:

$$J \cdot \frac{d\vec{\omega}}{dt} + \vec{\omega} \times J \cdot \vec{\omega} = \vec{M}_{total} \quad (1)$$

where J is the moment of inertia matrix, $\vec{\omega}$ is the angular velocity of the CubeSat in its body-frame, and \vec{M}_{total} is the sum of all angular moments applied to the main axes of the body.

Such equation is used to analyze the effect of several external torques that affect the satellite's attitude, through the inertia matrix. The rotational kinematic equations will specify the changes in the satellite's attitude angles as a function of the angular rates.

The net torque over the satellite during its space flight is composed by four main environmental factors: the gravity, the atmospheric density, the geomagnetic field, and the control torque. Other torques, such as solar radiation, will be disregarded, as they have negligible magnitude for a CubeSat at the altitudes studied in this work [11].

A. Gravity Gradient Torque

Torques due to gravity are fundamental to the attitude dynamics of a spacecraft. If the Earth's gravitational field is uniform over the body, the center of mass would become the center of gravity, and the gravitational torque would be zero. However, as the gravitational field is not uniform in space, this gradient of gravity over the body generates a moment around the center of mass. Thus, the gravity gradient torque is caused by the difference in distance from Earth through the satellite's body [8].

Fig 1 represents this phenomenon, with both forces pointing towards the center of the Earth, and $|f_2| > |f_1|$ due to the shown satellite orientation in the figure. Due to its proximity to the Earth, the magnitude of force f_2 is bigger than the force f_1 .

The gravity gradient torque is given by equation (2)

$$\vec{M}_{gg} = \frac{3\mu}{R} (\vec{u}_e \times J \vec{u}_e) \quad (2)$$

with \vec{u}_e being the unit vector pointed at Nadir, a vector that originates from the center of mass of the satellite and points to the center of the Earth [12]; R is the distance from the center of the Earth to the satellite; and μ is the geocentric gravitational constant.

B. Aerodynamic Torque

The atmosphere is extremely important due to its influence on the orbit decay, mainly for low-orbit satellites (LEO). The translational forces, due to drag, cause the speed of the body to decrease, which results in the reentry of the satellite. Furthermore, atmospheric drag induces moments for an asymmetric spacecraft [7].

The force due to the impact of atmospheric molecules on the spacecraft can be modeled as an elastic impact without reflection, that is, the energy that the molecule carried with it is

completely absorbed by the body of the satellite [13]. The force differential $d\vec{f}_{aero}$ on a surface element with area dA , with its normal vector pointing outside the body \hat{N} , is given by equation (3).

Fig 1 : Earth's gravity gradient torque over a CubeSat.

$$d\vec{f}_{aero} = -\frac{1}{2} C_d \rho_{ar} V^2 (\hat{N} \cdot \hat{V}) \hat{V} dA \quad (3)$$

\hat{V} is the unit vector in the translational direction of speed \vec{V} ; ρ_{ar} is the atmospheric density, and C_d the drag coefficient. The aerodynamic torque acting on the satellite due to the force $d\vec{f}_{aero}$ is as shown in equation (4):

$$\vec{M}_{aero} = \int_A \vec{r} \times d\vec{f}_{aero} \quad (4)$$

In this equation, \vec{r} is the vector between the satellite's center of mass and the surface of the dA element [13].

C. Magnetic Torque

When the satellite is immersed in a magnetic field, and the vehicle has a magnetic moment (from embedded magnets), torque can be identified [8]. As shown in Fig 2, it is possible to identify the two vectors: the magnetic field vector $\vec{B} = \vec{B}_{Earth}$ and the magnetic dipole vector \vec{m} due to the magnets. In addition, there is a difference between their directions, then producing a magnetic torque.

This torque is represented by the following equation (5)

$$\vec{M}_{mag} = \vec{m} \times \vec{B}_{Earth} \quad (5)$$

where \vec{m} is the moment of the magnetic dipole, and \vec{B}_{Earth} is the local geomagnetic field.

As a first approximation, the Earth's magnetic field can be modeled as a simple dipole (L-Shell Model). Each dipole value is obtained at a given instant, according to the satellite's position in orbit. The vector should be rotated to body-frame coordinates in accordance with the actual attitude of the satellite.

Fig 2 : Geomagnetic torque on the satellite.

D. Hysteresis Torque Methodology

In order to damp the satellite's rotation due to the resultant magnetic torque, some hysteresis rods are properly placed into the CubeSat's body. These rods are made of strong ferromagnetic materials, which will dissipate energy during the process of attitude correction of the satellite [12]. The hysteresis magnetic materials have significantly higher permeability than permanent magnets. Hence, the hysteresis materials tend to show a dynamic realignment of micro-magnetic dipoles when immersed in a variable magnetic field. These changes cause frictional dissipation of energy at the molecular level, and this phenomenon is known as hysteresis dissipation [14].

The torque generated by the hysteresis bar has the same format as the magnetic torque, which is given in equation (6):

$$M_{hist} = \vec{m}_{hist} \times \vec{B}_{Earth} \quad (6)$$

However, this equation demands the components of the magnetic dipole moment vector produced by the hysteresis bar, given by the following equation (7) [14]:

$$\vec{m}_{hist} = \frac{B_{hist} \vec{V}_{hist}}{\mu_0} \quad (7)$$

Where \vec{V}_{hist} is the volume vector of the hysteresis rod, which represents the material volumes used in the axes X_{CS}, Y_{CS}, Z_{CS} , μ_0 is the permeability in vacuum, and B_{hist} the magnetic induction provided by the hysteresis.

III. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The main objective of this work is to analyze the passive magnetic attitude control method by using an orbital simulation. The methodology consists in the mathematical modeling of the satellite's orbital dynamics, the torques that affect your attitude during your flight, and the control system influence. The whole simulation was implemented in the *Simulink*® environment, a *MatLab*® tool. The problem was modeled using block diagrams,

as shown in Fig 3. Each block performs a specific part of the solution of the differential equations associated with the rotational and translational movement of the satellite.

A. Orbit Propagation

The two-body problem was used to carry out the orbit propagation, considering only the effects of the Earth's mass over the satellite. The equation for determining the satellite's location coordinates in an inertial fixed system located at the center of the Earth is shown from equation (8) [15]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{gf}(t) \\ Y_{gf}(t) \\ Z_{gf}(t) \end{bmatrix} = R_{\Omega} R_i R_{\omega} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(f) \\ \sin(f) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \frac{h^2}{\mu} \left(\frac{1}{1+e \cos(f)} \right) \quad (8)$$

Where R_{Ω} , R_i and R_{ω} are given in equations (9) to (11):

$$R_{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Omega) & -\sin(\Omega) & 0 \\ \sin(\Omega) & \cos(\Omega) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$R_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(i) & -\sin(i) \\ 0 & \sin(i) & \cos(i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{\omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\omega) & -\sin(\omega) & 0 \\ \sin(\omega) & \cos(\omega) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

In addition, X_{gf} , Y_{gf} and Z_{gf} are the cartesian coordinates of the satellite's location; f is the true anomaly; h is the magnitude of the specific angular moment of the orbit; μ is the gravitational parameter; e is the orbit eccentricity, and Ω , i and ω are the longitude of the ascending node, the inclination and the argument of periapsis of the satellite's orbit, respectively [16]. All orbital parameters are calculated and updated at every iteration by the classic equations of the two-body problem [17]. Fig 4 shows a view of the orbit and the inertial reference system present in the above equations.

After finding the satellite position in the orbit, described in the inertial system, the local geomagnetic field is calculated. This field is modeled as a dipole that rotates together with the Earth (L-Shell Model). To calculate the magnetic field, it is necessary to compensate it, due to the longitudinal axis of this dipole is not perfectly aligned with the geographic north [18].

After determining the value of the field by the dipole models, it is necessary to perform a translation using the Euler's angles. This is done to obtain the local magnetic field in the body-frame system, in order to calculate the magnetic and hysteresis torques. This translation is done as presented in equation (12) [8]:

$$\vec{B}^{body} = C(\phi, \gamma, \rho) \vec{B}^{inertial} \quad (12)$$

Fig 3 : Mathematical simulation for the translational and rotational of a CubeSat in SIMULINK

Fig 4 : Satellite position at SGF axis system (fixed at the Earth's center and non-rotating).

Fig 5 : Drag coefficient estimation from a Monte Carlo simulation (DMCS) [21]

B. Aerodynamic Torque Methodology

The Kármán line is a frontier used to define the boundary between Earth's atmosphere and space. It is located 100 km above sea level, because at that altitude the Knudsen number (ratio between the free mean path and the representative physical length of the body) is greater than one. Thus, the interaction between the molecules is neglected, due to the low atmospheric density, and only the interaction between the gas

and the studied solid surface occurs [20].

One of the challenges for the aerodynamic torque calculation is to know the drag coefficient for a cube under the flow conditions of free molecules. As the flow is rarefied, it is not possible to use tools like computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Thus, it is necessary to use methods such as finite plate elements or direct Monte Carlo simulation (DMCS) [21].

By using a specularity factor of 25%, DSMC models and finite plate elements provide the same result for the drag coefficient of a cube when imposing a rarefied flow at an altitude of 300 km [21]. In Fig 5, the drag coefficient estimation for a 1U CubeSat is presented. By using such data, the drag coefficient is interpolated through the actual satellite rotation at the X and Z axes in the body frame.

The speed that must be taken into account, when calculating the torque is not just the speed of the CubeSat, but the relative speed of the atmosphere in relation to the satellite, in the body-frame system [22]. Thus, the local atmospheric velocity for a rotating terrestrial atmosphere is described by equation (13):

$$\vec{V}_r = V \left[1 - \left(\frac{\omega_E R}{V} \right) \cos(i) \right] C \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ \left(\frac{\omega_E R}{V} \right) \sin(i) \cos(f) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where V is the magnitude of the satellite's orbital speed, R is the distance to the center of Earth, ω_E is the terrestrial angular speed and $C(\varphi, \gamma, \rho)$ is the global matrix defined by Euler's Theorem. Therefore, the magnitude of the speed that goes into the calculation of the aerodynamic torque is the magnitude of \vec{V}_r .

In addition, it is possible to assume that the atmospheric density declines exponentially with the altitude [12]. It is also

possible to assume a spherically symmetric distribution of particles, where the density ρ_{ar} varies according to equation (14):

$$\rho_{ar} = \rho_0 \exp\left(-\left(\frac{h_{ellp}-h_0}{H}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

Where ρ_0 is the reference density, which is used with the reference altitude h_0 , h_{ellp} is the altitude of the satellite, and H is a scalar weight.

Fig 6 : CubeSat face elements for aerodynamic torque calculation.

In order to describe all the variables necessary to calculate aerodynamic force and torque, it is still necessary to solve (4). A common alternative is to represent the studied body as a collection of simple geometries, such as flat plates. Furthermore, from the surface division in a model composed of n flat plates, with each plate having a normal vector \hat{N}_i pointed out of the body and area A_i , the torque is represented by equation (15) [23]:

$$\vec{M}_{aero} = \sum_{i=1}^n \vec{r}_i \times \vec{F}_{aero,i} \quad (14)$$

with the aerodynamic force due to a given flat plate equals to value computed by equation (16):

$$\vec{F}_{aero,i} = -\frac{1}{2}\rho_{ar}C_dV_r^2A_i(\hat{N}_i \cdot \hat{V})\hat{V}. \quad (15)$$

Fig 6 shows an example of element division, with the vector \vec{r}_i , the vector \hat{N}_i and the velocity \vec{V} .

Fig 7: Hysteresis curve for a typical ferromagnetic material.

C. Hysteresis Torque Methodology

Hysteresis materials are defined by three parameters: saturation induction B_m (Tesla); the remnant induction B_0 (Tesla); and coercivity H_0 (Ampere/meter). Using these three parameters, equation (17) is applied to model the hysteresis of the material [12]:

$$B_{hist} = \frac{2B_m}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{H_0} \tan \left(\frac{\pi B_0}{2B_m} \right) (H \pm H_0) \right]. \quad (16)$$

Note that the term $\pm H_0$ can have two values, depending on the nature of the magnetic field. Thus, the positive value will be used when $dH/dt < 0$, and the negative value will be used when $dH/dt > 0$. The magnetic behavior of the hysteresis rod can be depicted as in Fig 7. The mathematical modeling of hysteresis from equation (17) can become complicated. An alternative is to use an algorithm to acquire an approximation from empirical tests, which leads to few simpler equations. This paper adopted the methodology proposed by [24].

D. Euler's Equation Methodology

After modeling the moments over satellite body due to the space environment, the Euler's equation (1) can be used to calculate the rotational dynamics of the body. A simplification can be applied, by assuming the CubeSat's mass distribution perfectly symmetric along its axes. This results that the inertia matrix can be written as a diagonal matrix as given in (18):

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & -I_{xy} & -I_{xz} \\ -I_{xy} & I_{yy} & -I_{yz} \\ -I_{xz} & -I_{yz} & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The angular velocity vector $\vec{\omega}$ can be written as given in (19):

$$\vec{\omega} = \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where p , q and r represent the satellite angular speeds in the body frame over x , y and z respectively. Thus, the equations for the rotational movement collapses to set of equations in (20) [8]:

$$\begin{cases} I_{xx}\dot{p} + (I_{zz} - I_{yy})qr = M_x \\ I_{yy}\dot{q} + (I_{xx} - I_{zz})pr = M_y \\ I_{zz}\dot{r} + (I_{yy} - I_{xx})pq = M_z \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

To obtain the respective speed in the inertial axes, a matrix rotation is yet necessary:

$$\begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = T_M^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

being as represented by (22),

$$T_M^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\sin(\gamma) \\ 0 & \cos(\phi) & \sin(\phi)\cos(\gamma) \\ 0 & -\sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi)\cos(\gamma) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

Conversely, the Euler's angles can be obtained from the values for p , q and r as given in equation (23):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\gamma} \\ \dot{\rho} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tan(\gamma)\sin(\phi) & \tan(\gamma)\cos(\phi) \\ 0 & \cos(\phi) & -\sin(\phi) \\ 0 & \frac{\sin(\phi)}{\cos(\gamma)} & \frac{\cos(\phi)}{\cos(\gamma)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Now, the necessary equations for numerical simulation of the satellite were obtained. The translational and rotational movement are described by equations (8) and (23) respectively. The torques that actuates over the CubeSat body, affecting the body rotational speeds, are given by equations (2) and (4) – (6) (and the related equations). By working with these equations, it is possible to obtain the whole orbital movement of the CubeSat.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, the results obtained by the simulator described in the previous sections will be presented. As explained, the core of the passive magnetic control strategy is to implant magnets and hysteresis rods into the CubeSat's body, so that the satellite follows the geomagnetic field lines. Two materials were selected to such task: alnico-5 magnets and HyMu-80 alloy as dissipative element. The alnico-5 magnet has a coercivity field of 50,900 A/m and a remnant induction of 1.28T, while HyMu-80 alloy rates 1.59 A/m and 0.35 T for the same parameters, respectively. Additionally, the HyMu-80 alloy has a saturation induction of 0.73 T.

The alnico-5 magnets were placed so that the magnetic dipole at the X axis is 0.7A/m (and zero at the other axes). The magnetic damping HyMu-80 alloy was distributed along the X, Y and Z body axis in the following material volume (in mm³): 5, 70 and 70.

It was considered an 1U CubeSat with main inertia moments given by: $I_{xx} = 0.00182 \text{ kg.m}^2$, $I_{yy} = 0.00185 \text{ kg.m}^2$ and $I_{zz} = 0.00220 \text{ kg.m}^2$. To calculate the aerodynamic forces, each CubeSat's face was split in 25 regular elements.

To perform the simulation, some initial conditions were assumed. The initial inertial angles are assumed as 0 degrees at all the axes, while the initial angular speed was set as $\omega_{x0} = 6\text{deg./sec}$, $\omega_{y0} = 3\text{deg./sec}$, and $\omega_{z0} = 4\text{deg./sec}$. The simulation was performed by considering different conditions for the altitude and the orbit eccentricity and inclination. The simulation was run for a time window around three hours, which covers around two orbital periods for a 300km orbit.

A. Case 1: 300km circular equatorial orbit

This simulation case involves a circular orbit, with altitude of 300 km and null inclination. Initially, the disturbing torques were obtained from the simulation and compared through their RMS (root mean squared) value along the simulation time window. The results are condensed in TABLE 1 where the results are split in each of the environmental torque contribution.

Some conclusions can be drawn about such values. The magnetic torques amount considerably higher values when compared to the aerodynamic and gravity contributions. This is

an expected result since the former represents the control torque used to align the CubeSat. Between the disturbance torques, the aerodynamic is the most important. The gravity torque has a negligible contribution, at least for such CubeSat configuration.

TABLE 1
RMS torque values in each body axis.

axis	RMS Torque [$N \cdot m$]			
	Disturbing		Control	
	Aerodynamic	Gravity	Hysteresis	Magnetic
X_b	0.134×10^{-8}	4.253×10^{-10}	2.091×10^{-7}	2.091×10^{-7}
Y_b	1.207×10^{-8}	3.303×10^{-10}	5.581×10^{-7}	5.581×10^{-7}
Z_b	2.158×10^{-8}	0.263×10^{-10}	5.631×10^{-7}	5.631×10^{-7}

Since the control objective is to align one of the axes with the local geomagnetic field, it is necessary to analyze such behavior in the orbital flight. This is achieved by writing the local geomagnetic field vector at the CubeSat's body frame. In an alignment condition, the geomagnetic vector is perfectly aligned with the body axis that received the magnets (X axis in our case). Then, the angle of the local geomagnetic vector in relation to X axis should tend to zero. The other body axis should converge to an angle of 90 degrees from the local geomagnetic vector.

Obviously, it does not mean that body-frame angles are static in relation to the inertial frame. Such body angles are changing along the flight to achieve a perfect alignment with the local geomagnetic field.

The results for this case are presented in Fig 9. Notice that the satellite demands around 2.25 hours to achieve the steady state condition. This represents 1.5 orbital periods. As expected, the geomagnetic field vector, written in body axis, converges to the X body axis, indicating the alignment. This vector also converges to 90 degrees in relation to Y and Z axes. In this way, the CubeSat maintains the alignment along the orbital flight, as desired.

Fig 8 : Local geomagnetic field written in CubeSat's body frame along the orbital flight.

(Conditions: Altitude = 300 Km, $i = 0 \text{ deg}$, $e = 0$)

Another important analysis takes into account the angular speed of the CubeSat in relation to the local geomagnetic field. Those axes that receive more ferromagnetic material tend to exhibit a neglected angular speed with respect to the local field vector, due to the hysteresis magnetic damping. Conversely, the axis with less ferromagnetic material experiments some angular

speed.

For the CubeSat under study, the higher amount of ferromagnetic material is placed at Y and Z axes. Then, the angular speed around these axes should be negligible. For X axis, which received a small quantity of damping material, it is expected a small angular speed around it. Fig 9 confirms the expectations. The angular speed around Y and Z body axes tends to zero, while the speed around the X approaches to a very low value: less than 1 rpm.

Fig 9 : CubeSat's angular speed along the orbital flight.
(Conditions: Altitude = 300 Km, $i = 0$ deg, $e = 0$)

B. Case 2: 600km circular equatorial orbit

In this case, the orbital altitude is increased to 600 km. As this simulation is very similar to the last one, only the alignment condition is presented in Fig 10. Again, the passive control system was able to align the CubeSat after around 2.2 orbital periods.

Fig 10 : Local geomagnetic field written in CubeSat's body frame along the orbital flight.
(Conditions: Altitude = 600 Km, $i = 0$ deg, $e = 0$)

C. Case 3: 600km circular orbit, with inclination of 45 degrees

In this case, an orbit with 45 degrees of inclination is considered. Fig 11 shows the result. It is interesting to highlight the fact that the accommodation period is greater than the case which the inclination is zero. This is due to the higher variations of the geomagnetic field along the flight, thus delaying the dissipation of energy by the control system.

D. Case 4: elliptic orbit with perigee of 600km and inclination of 45 degrees

This test considers an elliptic orbit with eccentricity of 0.0071 and perigee of 600 km. The inclination was maintained 45 degrees. The results are in Fig 12.

Fig 11 : Local geomagnetic field written in CubeSat's body frame along the orbital flight.
(Conditions: Altitude = 600 Km, $i = 45$ deg, $e = 0$)

Fig 12 : Local geomagnetic field written in CubeSat's body frame along the orbital flight.
(Conditions: Altitude = 600 Km, $i = 0$ deg, $e = 0.0071$)

There is a slight difference between circular and elliptical orbits. The reason is that the satellite faces different altitudes along the flight in an elliptic orbit, and so different magnitudes of the geomagnetic strength. This results in smaller control torques and a slower alignment time. Such effect is so more intense as the higher the orbit eccentricity.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this paper is to discuss a complete numerical simulation of the orbital flight of CubeSats. Both translational and rotational dynamics are considered, as well the main environmental disturbing torques that actuate on the nanosatellite. In addition, it is also presented a passive control system based on the interaction between the Earth's magnetic field and magnetic dipole included into the satellite body. Several examples were explored, confirming the procedure efficacy.

Some novel contributions are included in this study. Firstly, a consistent procedure to obtain the aerodynamic torque over the CubeSat's body is reported. Although this disturbing effect

presents marginal contribution for satellites with 1U configuration, it can be important for larger CubeSat's or with big appendages. Another relevant fact is the possibility to simulate the satellite flight for any kind of orbit (inclination and eccentricity). Most of the literature considers only circular orbits.

The control strategy can be easily modified, even for the active case, which an automatic controller is responsible for autonomous adapting the flight variables according to desired restrictions. Basically, this can be done by changing the control torque forces based on the chosen methodology.

Many further studies can be derived from this paper. One of them consists in introducing different control methodologies. For CubeSats containing reaction wheels, cold gas and electrical propulsion, the mathematical models can be easily incorporated into the simulation. This improves the attitude control capability, providing better pointing precision. Furthermore, a more precise model for the geomagnetic field can be also used. A new simulation environment is being developed by the authors. The idea is to provide a modular simulation, which the user is able to choose many flight conditions and control strategies in an open-source code, freely available to the community. Such code is under development, and it will be presented soon.

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